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Title: SOP to flush the inlet components (sample transfer line and needle insert placed in H-ESI spray insert) of Orbitrap Exploris 480 MS by the LC after acquisition.

Date: 2025-03-01

Version: version 1

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If the mass spectrum is suspected to show contamination peaks, flush the inlet components with the LC. Flushing flowrate is applied for **HESI Hi Flow Needle Insert 100 um ID32G (OPTON-30694)** which is used for acquisition.

Make a note about flushing the inlet components by LC to Logbook.

SW: Xcalibur 4.7.69.37, Thermo Scientific for SII Xcalibur 1.7.0.468, Orbitrap Exploris Tune 4.3.458.15

To prepare LC prior to flushing

1. Replace the current LC bottles with those without buffers or additives, i.e., use the UCL/MS grade methanol and water one (Biosolve Chimie SARL).
2. Check that the column with precolumn was removed from the column oven.
3. In Orbitrap Exploris Tune Application (Tune window), place the divert valve to waste (1-6 position).

To flush the inlet components by the LC

1. If not, adjust the H-ESI spray insert to position 3.
2. In Tune window, place the MS to On Mode (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Power mode icons showing the selected mode

3. Open the panel ION SOURCE/Ion source, set the below defined values for H-ESI mode and click **Apply**.

Parameter	Heated-ESI mode
Ion Spray Voltage (V)*	0
Sheath Gas (Arbitrary Units)	30
Auxiliary Gas (Arbitrary Units)	5
Sweep Gas (Arbitrary Units)	0
Ion Transfer Tube Temperature (°C)	350
Vaporizer Temperature (°C)	400

*for positive and negative mode

4. In Tune window, wait till parameter values are reached, then set divert valve to MS (1-2 position).
5. Flush inlet components by 50:50 methanol/water solution at flowrate of 0.2 mL/min for 20 mins.
6. Turn Off the LC pumps to stop the flow, place the MS to Standby Mode and then adjust the H-ESI spray insert into position 2. Optionally, set divert valve to waste (1-6 position).

Note: The used figures were obtained from Orbitrap Exploris Series (Thermo Fisher Scientific): Operating Manual and OptaMax NG Ion Source User Guide.